

Falcon Team Description Paper 2024

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Abstract. Most of our focus has been on exponential functions, so that we have examined all its positions and examined them in the game with different teams until we finally reached a suitable algorithm. Algorithms that we worked extensively on include: dribble and press, the process of which is discussed below. We used an algorithm that divides the land transversely into six parts divides.

1 Keywords: Robocup , Soccer simulation 2D , Side Pass , Direct dribble.

2 Introduction

We started with the C++ programming language, where we were introduced to the general form of 2D simulation coding. Finally, with the progress of teamwork and team work, as well as participation in the 2D simulation league, we brought a high-quality football team to the field. The class league helped a lot to solve our team's problems. We also used a lot of new ideas in the team, most of which came from watching football in the real world. At the beginning of the game against the strong teams of the league, we conceded many goals. This gave us a chance to strengthen one of our biggest problems, which is our defense. Finally, we were able to model the opponent with the help of articles (Pourmehr and Dadkhah 2011), Simulation team description article (Wang, Huang et al.) Motion generation and analysis (Loureiro and Carneiro) Two-dimensional simulation team description article (Khashabi and Amoozgar 2010) As well as the simulation description article (Darijani, Mostaejran et al. 2016) Bring a standard and relatively professional team. These articles helped us a lot in finding ideas. For example, we used the explanations of the teams for the general algorithm of how to write the functions.

3 Side Pass

This pass is defined for players who are on the sidelines

In this pass, we examine the players using a repeating loop.

First, we define a triangle with the starting point of the player who owns the ball to the coordinates of the teammate. If there is no player in this triangle, it means that the passing path is safe. Again, we define a triangle for the teammate, which is the triangle with the angle of movement The player is defined in the coordinates of the side lines, if there is no player from the opponent inside this triangle and the player of our teammate is in the position of the side lines of the field, also if the position of the teammate is not lower than the player who owns the ball, the position of this player is inside a Vector is placed.

After the position of the right players is placed in the vector, we check which one of the coordinates is ahead of all, and we choose the coordinate which is ahead of all as the right player to pass. Then, in order to increase the speed of the attack, we check to determine whether it is possible to make a deep pass or not.

For this, we define a triangle from the coordinates of the player with the angle of his movement in the side lines. If there is no opponent player in this triangle, the coordinates of a few points ahead of the player's coordinates are obtained and the hit is made at the coordinates ahead of the player.

Figure 1- In this photo, we see player number 9 passing to player number 11

4 Direct dribble

We designed a type of dribble that moves straight from We used an algorithm that divides the land transversely into six parts divides.

- 3.1 In the first step, three triangles are defined for each part, in the first triangle it evaluates an average distance with a relatively large viewing angle.
- 3.2 If there is a teammate inside that triangle and the conditions of the pass if there is, a pass will be given to that player's teammate.
- 3.3 In the second triangle, a large distance and a smaller viewing angle are evaluated if there is no opponent player in this triangle, it gives the ball with It hits with more power and moves faster.
- 3.4 The third triangle with the same distance as the first triangle and with a smaller viewing angle than the first triangle is defined. If there is no opponent player in this triangle the player moves with a slower speed than the second triangle and hits the ball with it hits with less power.

The way this algorithm works is as follows: first of all, the case of the shot The review states that if it can be done, only the shot should be done If the shooting position is not available, evaluate the coordinates of the ball Places it so that if the ball is inside each of the defined areas The player had to move proportionally to the same area in the first triangle A teammate passes to him and considers the next situation It does not take, but if there is no teammate in the first triangle, it is the turn of the player Checking the absence of a player in the third triangle That if the opponent player In it, there was no opponent player in the second evaluated triangle It is assumed that if there is no player inside the second triangle with power move more, but if there is a player inside the second triangle, it is a condition Movement in the third triangle is confirmed. The same process is evaluated for all six districts.

5 Simple press

In the discussion of players' press, we have used a scoring system. In this system, three important factors are measured so that the player can choose the best opponent player to press. The three aspects that are examined are (Prokopenko and Wang 2019):

- 4.1 The distance between the player and the ball : First, we count the distance between all the opposing players and the ball. And the smaller this distance is. A higher score is given to that player for pressing, the highest score is 10 and the lowest is zero(Shi, Liu et al. 2008)
- 4.2 Distance from the player to the goal: In the next step, we calculate the distance between all the opposing players and the goal. The smaller this distance, the more points will be given to that player because the risk of this player scoring is higher.
- 4.3 The distance between the player and himself: At the end, we measure the accessibility of all the opposing players and each player who was closer to us gets a higher score.
- 4.4 Finally, in a function, we compare all three points given for each player, and the player with a higher point is pressed. Of course, if the desired player has already been pressed, he will only change the direction of his body towards the ball.

Figure 2- In this photo, player number 3 is giving points to opponent player number 11

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